

THE ESSENCE OF PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS AND ITS HISTORICAL IMPORTANCE IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the main attention was paid to the historical background of paremiology, which is part of phraseology along with phraseological units. Also, semantic and linguistic aspects of paremiological units in English and Uzbek languages were analyzed and proverbs were studied. English and Uzbek languages were compared linguistically and culturally

It is well recognized that language serves as the primary medium for interpersonal communication. Phraseological units of one or more languages play a significant role in the generational transmission of a particular people's national and cultural lifestyle, customs and traditions, folklore, art, and science. These units play a crucial role in each language's communication, and one cannot envision a language without its specific phraseological layer.

Like many other disciplines, modern linguistics has a thriving phraseology section. Numerous languages use animal names to describe a person's figurative traits. The zoomorphic lexicon is based on the attributes that humans have given to animals, either objectively or subjectively.

The usage of proverbs from a literary perspective was considered by the masters and representatives of both written and informal speech in order to enhance the creative quality of signs and works and to supply the fluency of the literary language. If we research in detail the works of Yusuf Hos Hojib, Ahmad Yassavi, Rabguzi, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Abulgazi Bakhadir Khan, Munis, Ogakhi, Nodira, Muqimi, Furkat, Avaz, Hamza, Sadridin Ayniy, Fitrat, Chulpan, Abdulla Qodiriy, Oybek, Gafur Gulam and many other linguist scholars we can find out that there are a huge number of proverbs in their own forms and also changed, modification forms. We should also point out that proverbs have inspired several literary works.

For instance, Sulayman Rojiy used more than 400 proverbs in his poetry "Zarbulmasal" and Mukhammad Sharif Gulhaniy's "Zarbulmasal" contains more than 300 proverbs. The organization of Uzbek national proverbs was started in order to create specific collections from them, which were then added to reader collections and contents starting in the second half of the 19th century. For instance, Hungarian scholar H. Vamberi produced the reader-dictionary «Textbook on the Chigatay language» («Chig'atoy tili darsligi») in Leipzig in 1867.

This dictionary features 112 proverbs with their German translations along with some examples of Uzbek literature and folklore.

A. Naumov (1985), N. Gatsunayev (1983, 1988), and Y. Chernyavskiy (1959) all put in a lot of effort to publish collections of Uzbek national proverbs in the Russian language. The fact that these collections were published at various times and in various years greatly influenced the gathering of national proverbs, their proper arrangement, and the dissemination of factual information contained therein. However, they vary in terms of the quantity of materials, selection, and theme division.

Despite being extremely old, proverbs are always regarded as a modern genre. Their age goes back as far as national history. Proverbs and sayings from specific countries often reflect their unique socioeconomic characteristics. This category allows us to specify the time period to which they belong. – based on the structure. The quantity of logical centers that proverbs have causes them to be divided into the following categories. Alternatively stated: components, components, components, and more. Uzbek proverbs were initially categorized using the aforementioned elements. There is currently a further classification method: In accordance with the essence of their antonyms or synonyms. Proverbs are arranged in alphabetical order to encompass synonym and antonym variations.

References in Uzbek paremiology that are written using alphabetically ordered and themes-based classification methods include «O'zbek xalq maqollari» (1987, 2 volumes), «O'zbek xalq maqollari» (1989, several volumes), «O'zbek xalq maqollari» (2003), and etymology-based collections «Hikmatnoma» (1990) by Sh.

Phraseology was developed by several Uzbek scholars, including Shavkat Rahmatullayev, who in turn played a vital impact in phraseology's birth in Uzbek linguistics. The phraseology of the Uzbek language was greatly influenced by a number of his scientific studies in the area of phraseology. His "Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," "Short Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," "Main Meaning Types of Phraseological Combinations," and "Osnovnie grammatichicheskie osobennosti obraznix" are among the phraseological combinations with the most common meanings. With a number of scientific works, including "glagolnix frazeologicheskikh yedinetsov sovremennogo uzbekskogo yazika," he made contributions to the phraseology of the Uzbek language. He had significant success studying phraseological units, including Y. Pinkhasov.

His publications "Current Uzbek Literary Language" and "About the Phraseology of the Uzbek Language" made a contribution. In addition to B. Yoldoshev, Abdugofur, and Abdumurad Mamatov, these individuals had a big influence on the growth of Uzbek phraseology.

In summary, phraseology is one of the areas of linguistics that is thought to have a brief history. For many years, it was studied as a component of lexicology before becoming a separate department. Despite the fact that phraseology has been the subject of extensive study, there are still many unrecognized features.

References:

1. Rasulov. R. Berdiyeva H. Paremiological dictionary of the Uzbek language. T.: Teacher, 1984, 286 p. – P.7.

2. PAREMIOLOGY AS A STUDY OBJECT OF PHRASEOLOGY. Ruzikulov Elyor Shukurovich
3. O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati. Shavkat Rahmatullayev. "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti
4. Irgasheva Feruza Bakhtiyorovna. (2021). INTEGRATION OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE INTO THE TRANSLATION PROCESS. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE, 2(1), 32-34. Retrieved from <http://cajlp.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/56>
5. Imamkulova Sitara Anvarovna. (2021). Cognitive Interpretation of Degrees of Intensification. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 11(1). Retrieved from <https://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/469>
- 6.
7. Djalolov F. F. "To the problems of complete assimilation of educational materials at schools" European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA) Vol. 1 No. 4, December 2020.p.55-57
8. Salikhova Nodira Nurullayevna. (2020). THE KEY OF EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION IS PRONUNCIATION. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 1(4), 5-7.